

Cloud Masking For CoastWatch Satellite Imagery

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Abstract - A cloud mask program is available for masking out all clouds present on CoastWatch satellite imagery products. CoastWatch satellite imagery are operational NOAA polar-satellite 1 km Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) data that are remapped for designated U.S. coastal regions. Sea surface temperature imagery is one of the current CoastWatch products; however, the product contains cloudy pixels. A cloud mask product is necessary to determine cloud free areas for sea surface temperature identification. The Clouds from AVHRR (CLAVR) cloud detection algorithm is being tested on both day and night AVHRR imagery. An explanation of the cloud masking tests and examples of their application to the analysis of sea surface temperature imagery for the coastal U.S. on a near-real time basis are presented in this paper.

I. INTRODUCTION

Analysis of CoastWatch satellite sea surface temperature and visible imagery of U.S. coastal areas is hindered by the presence of cloud contamination. An automated cloud-mask product has been developed for use in cloud screening these satellite images. A description of CoastWatch, the satellite imagery, and the cloud mask algorithm "Clouds from AVHRR" (CLAVR), and some examples of the application of CLAVR to CoastWatch imagery are presented in this paper.

II. COASTWATCH

One of the missions of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) of the United States Department of Commerce is to manage the Nation's ocean and coastal resources. CoastWatch, an established theme

within the NOAA Coastal Ocean Program, contributes information for managing coastal living marine resources and ecosystems by providing satellite and other environmental coastal monitoring information.

Satellite imagery for U.S. coastal areas is created from near real-time satellite data and provided via an established number of regional sites along the coastal United States ("Fig. 1"). These CoastWatch regional sites distribute this imagery to their local users, that include: state natural resource managers; federal agencies; and university researchers. CoastWatch products for the Gulf of Mexico, the U.S. East Coast, and the Great Lakes are produced centrally and distributed to CoastWatch regional sites via Internet. The West Coast, Alaska, and Hawaii CoastWatch regional sites obtain satellite data from local readout stations and produce CoastWatch products locally for distribution to users.

III. SATELLITE MAPPED IMAGE PRODUCTS FOR COASTWATCH

Currently, satellite-derived products for CoastWatch consist of mapped visible and Sea Surface Temperature (SST) imagery derived from Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) data. AVHRR instruments fly on NOAA operational polar orbiting environmental satellites, of which there are generally two operational at the same time. To date only NOAA-11 (the afternoon/night satellite) has been utilized for CoastWatch products. CoastWatch products from NOAA-12 (the morning/evening satellite) are being added during the fall of 1993. The AVHRR is a scanning radiometer which measures radiation in the spectral intervals given in Table 1 [1].

This work was supported in part by the NOAA Coastal Ocean Program. This footnote is not numbered.

TABLE 1
 ADVANCED VERY HIGH RESOLUTION RADIOMETER
 (AVHRR/2)
 INSTRUMENT CHANNELS

<u>CHANNEL</u>	<u>SPECTRAL RANGE</u> (micrometers)	<u>USE IN COASTWATCH</u>
1	0.58 - 0.68 μ m } 2	day clouds & turbidity
3	0.73 - 1.10 μ m }	
4	3.55 - 3.93 μ m }	day/night clouds
5	10.3 - 11.3 μ m } 11.5 - 12.5 μ m }	day/night clouds & SST

The AVHRR infrared channels (Channels 3, 4, and 5) are calibrated using an on-board black-body target and deep space. The visible and reflected IR channels (Channels 1 and 2) are not calibrated.

Whenever the NOAA-11 satellite passes over one of the CoastWatch regions (generally 2-3 times/day), the AVHRR data over the region are mapped to a Mercator projection at nearly full resolution (1.2 km). All five channels, the satellite zenith angle and the solar zenith angle are mapped for daytime passes.¹ For nighttime passes, only the infrared channels and the zenith angles are mapped. These channel and angle region maps are sectorized and combined and used to produce all of the CoastWatch satellite image products. Most CoastWatch images are 512 X 512 pixel arrays formed either by sectorizing (i.e., cutting out) a square array from the region maps at full resolution or by subsampling to form lower-resolution (4 km) synoptic images. SST images are formed by employing a non-linear multichannel SST equation using the thermal split window channels (i.e., Channels 4 and 5). A correction for look angle is also made using the satellite zenith angle. In cloud-free and aerosol-free areas the accuracy of the SST measurements is in the range 0.5-0.8 °C root-mean-square difference as measured against drifting buoy SST's. "Fig. 2" is an example of a synoptic SST image for the Northeast U.S. coast.

IV. COASTWATCH CLOUD-MASK PRODUCT REQUIREMENTS

A cloud-mask CoastWatch image product has been under development to add to the operational SST, channel, and angle products. This product:

¹ The zenith angle of a point on the earth is the angle between the local vertical at that point and a line connecting the point and the satellite or the sun.

1) aids in the interpretation of AVHRR CoastWatch imagery because it is not always obvious what is a cloud and what is an ocean thermal feature;

2) allows automatic multi-day compositing of SST images so that only cloud-free image pixels are composited;

3) provides a simple automated way to determine the number of cloud-free pixels in an image for use in image screening so that excessively cloudy images do not have to be downloaded to users needing cloud-free imagery; and

4) aids in the automatic production of a cloud-free buoy-satellite SST match up data base for product quality control and accuracy assessment.

The cloud-mask product which has been developed, but not yet implemented operationally, consists of an 8-bit graphics file which matches pixel-for-pixel with the satellite imagery. This file can overlay the image in an 8-bit graphics plane. The cloud-mask file is actually eight individual 1-bit planes, each for a different cloud test. With appropriate software, the entire cloud mask or individual 1-bit planes can be toggled on and off to aid in analyzing the imagery underneath. Nineteen different cloud tests have been programmed into the CoastWatch image mapping software; however, only a subset of these have been selected for operational implementation. The set selected is a subset of the Clouds from AVHRR (CLAVR) cloud algorithm (Stowe, et al., 1991).

V. CLOUDS FROM AVHRR (CLAVR) TECHNIQUE

The CLAVR cloud detection algorithm was designed to classify 4-km resolution Global Area Coverage (GAC) AVHRR data as clear, cloudy, partly cloudy, or unknown. Classification is accomplished by means of a sequence of threshold tests applied to 2x2 GAC pixel arrays. These tests identify the presence of clouds based on the differences between the radiative and physical properties of clouds and the underlying surface of the Earth. The key elements in this testing procedure are based on:

1) intensity discrimination against the background;

2) multispectral differences and ratios; and 3) spatial uniformity. A different series of tests are invoked depending on whether the observation is day or night and also whether the background is land or sea. See [2] for details of the cloud tests. CoastWatch employs a subset of the ocean day and night CLAVR cloud tests, using the CLAVR thresholds. The CoastWatch implementation of CLAVR differs from the original technique applied to GAC data in the following ways:

1. CLAVR is applied to single pixel or 2X2 pixel arrays of full-resolution High Resolution Picture Transmission (HPRT) AVHRR data rather than 2X2 pixel arrays of GAC data.

2. The ocean cloud tests are used for both ocean and land since CoastWatch is only concerned with coastal ocean processes and the coastal boundary is not yet known to a 1-2 pixel accuracy without interactive interpretation.

3. Every cloud test is applied to each pixel rather than applying the cloud tests in sequence and stopping when one cloud test shows the presence of a cloud. This allows an analyst to turn off individual cloud tests which in certain cases are too conservative, such as the infrared uniformity test which rejects the edges of cloud-free high-gradient ocean features.

4. Pixels are classified as only clear or cloudy. Partly cloudy or unknown arrays of pixels are classified as cloudy.

5. Restoral cloud tests are not currently being used since they generally apply to ocean areas above 50° of latitude.

The daytime and nighttime CLAVR cloud test thresholds for ocean scenes for the CoastWatch subset of CLAVR tests are in Table 2. A pixel or array of pixels is cloudy if the threshold criteria is met. An explanation of each of the cloud tests is given following the table.

TABLE 2

CLAVR CLOUD TESTS USED BY COASTWATCH

<u>TEST</u>	<u>DAY/NIGHT</u>	<u>CHANNEL(S)</u>	<u>THRESHOLD</u>
RGCT	DAY	2	> 20%
RUT	DAY	2	> 0.3%
RRCT	DAY	2/1	0.9 < R < 1.1
C3AT	DAY	3,4,5	> 3%
TUT	DAY & NIGHT	4	> 0.5°K
FMFT	DAY & NIGHT	4,5	> fcn T4
TGCT	DAY & NIGHT	4	< 271°K
ULST	NIGHT	3,5	< fcn T4
CIRT	NIGHT	3,5	> fcn T4

(fcn - Function)

RGCT - Reflective Gross Cloud Test

This test rejects pixels contaminated with highly reflective clouds as seen in Channel 2. The threshold is set high enough to pass aerosols, haze, and some, but not all, sun glint. Sea and lake ice will be erroneously classified as cloudy.

RUT - Reflectance Uniformity Test

This test is applied to 2X2 pixel arrays. If the difference between the maximum and minimum Channel 2 reflectance in the array is greater than 0.3%, the entire array is classified as cloudy. Such a small threshold can be used because an ocean scene without clouds is very uniformly reflective.

RRCT - Reflectance Ratio Cloud Test

This cloud test computes the ratio of Channel 2 to Channel 1 (R). If this ratio is between 0.9 and 1.1, the presence of clouds is indicated.

C3AT - Channel 3 Albedo Test

This test is used to detect residual cirrus or sub-pixel cloudiness overlooked by other cloud tests. Channel 3 senses reflected radiation as well as emitted thermal radiation. This cloud test estimates the emitted radiation in Channel 3 by using Channels 4 and 5, allowing the reflected radiation in Channel 3 to be calculated. If the

reflectance is greater than 3%, clouds are assumed to exist. The success of this test is based on the greater sensitivity of AVHRR Channel 3 to reflected solar radiation from clouds than from aerosols.

TUT - Thermal Uniformity Test

Like the RUT, the TUT is applied to 2X2 pixel arrays. The entire array is classified as cloudy if the difference between the maximum and minimum Channel 4 temperature exceeds 0.5°K. Exceeding this limit suggests a non-uniform area, most probably due to the presence of clouds. This test erroneously classifies high ocean thermal gradients in the ocean (such as the north wall of the Gulf Stream) as cloudy.

FMFT - Channel 4 Minus 5 Test

This test is primarily used to detect thin cirrus clouds which can have larger differences between the Channel 4 and 5 temperatures than are caused by water vapor attenuation. The threshold for this test is a function of the Channel 4 temperature.

TGCT - Thermal Gross Cloud Test

This test examines the Channel 4 temperature versus a threshold of 271°K over ocean. Great Lakes ice will be misclassified as clouds with this threshold.

ULST - Uniform Low Stratus Test

This test is used to detect low stratus clouds at night which often escape the TGCT and TUT tests. The ULST is based on the difference between Channel 3 and Channel 5 temperatures versus a threshold determined as a function of the Channel 4 temperature.

CIRT - Cirrus Test

The Cirrus Test (CIRT) is defined as the difference between the Channel 3 and 5 temperatures divided by the Channel 5 temperature. A Channel 4-dependent threshold is again used to implicitly account for water vapor effects.

VI. EXAMPLES OF CLOUD-MASK IMAGERY

To illustrate the cloud-mask product, a cloud-mask was generated for the Northeast U.S. Synoptic region SST image shown in "Fig. 2." This July 6, 1993 image shows

the U.S. East Coast from South Carolina to the Maine coast at night. The land is masked out in black. The Gulf Stream is very distinct as a dark band of water and two eddies are visible (cold and warm eddy, A and B, respectively). There are stratocumulus clouds present on the right side of the image with cumulus clouds in lines scattered through and south of the Gulf Stream. In the southern part of the image are multi-layer stratus, altostratus and towering cumulus clouds. Fog, most likely, rings Nova Scotia. "Fig. 3" shows the same SST image with all the cloud tests applied. Normally each cloud test is indicated by a different color, but for this paper they have all been assigned the color white. The areas in shades of gray are cloud-free sea surface temperatures. In regions of high surface thermal gradient some cloud-free areas are also masked, mainly by the TUT. "Fig. 4" shows the cloud mask tests with the Thermal Uniformity Test (TUT) absent. Comparing "Fig. 3 and 4," one can see how in "Fig. 3" the edges of the Gulf Stream and the eddies have been masked, but are clear in "Fig. 4". Without the TUT test, however, some clouds are not masked (Point C, D, E).

VIII. SUMMARY

With the few exceptions noted above, the CLAVR algorithm performs well in masking clouds in CoastWatch imagery. Before operational implementation, however, further testing is needed to fully determine the limitations of these tests when ice, aerosol, fog, and sunglint are present in the image.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank J. Sapper, C. Duda, K. Jarva, J. Stroup, and D. Morel for development and operational testing of the cloud-mask software, and D. Garey and K. Buttlemann for developing the image display software used to analyze the images.

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Fig. 1 CoastWatch Regional Sites

Fig. 2 CoastWatch Northeast synoptic SST image (July 6, 1993). Temperatures colder than 0^o C are white, dark greys are warm areas. A warm eddy is indicated by A and cold eddy by B.

Fig. 3 CoastWatch Northeast synoptic SST image (July 6, 1993) with CLA VR nighttime ocean cloud tests shown as white.

Fig. 4 CoastWatch Northeast synoptic SST image (July 6, 1993) with CLA VR nighttime ocean cloud tests as white except the thermal uniformity cloud test has not been applied. Clouds no longer masked are indicated by points C, D, and E.